
IN-DEPTH REVIEW OF CIVIC SPACES IN THE EU

The cases of Catalonia, Rome, Torino,
Torres Vedras and Warsaw

Deliverable 2.2

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*A democracy is more than a form of government;
it is primarily a mode of associated living,
of conjoint communicated experience.*

(J. Dewey)

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Introduction

The B.RIGHT SPACES project unites the experiences of civic spaces from four countries – Italy, Spain, Poland, and Portugal- through the perspectives of the consortium partners, who represent local authorities, civil society, and social-economy organisations. Unlike most academic literature on civic spaces, as well as studies conducted by international organisations regarding their development and shrinkage, the experiences of the B.RIGHT SPACES partners and their networks reveal more nuanced aspects of the conceptualization and practice of civic spaces, providing insights into regional and local peculiarities, struggles, and best practices.

This report provides an in-depth overview of civic spaces in the project territories: Catalonia (regional level), the metropolitan city of Rome (provincial level), Torino (large city), Torres Vedras (small town and rural area), and Warsaw (capital city). Our aim is to enhance the understanding of the diverse experiences of civic spaces and facilitate the knowledge and exchange of good practices.

The study features a comprehensive review of each territory, utilising qualitative methods (desk research, surveys, expert interviews, and focus groups), executed with significant contributions from the consortium partners – Generalitat de Catalunya (GENCAT), Xarxa d’Economia Solidària (XES), Associazione PARSEC, CSV Lazio, the Municipality of Turin, Fundacja Inicjatyw Społeczno-Ekonomicznych (FISE), the Municipality of Torres Vedras and EMERGE.

The presentation for each territory includes:

- A brief literature review reflecting recent research on the dynamics of civic spaces in these territories and the relationship between public authorities and civil society;
- A presentation of the national legal frameworks that regulate and define civic spaces, synthesised based on the insights of the Consortium partners;
- An exploration of specificities in understanding the concept of ‘civic space’ based on open responses provided to the Consortium’s proposed operational definition in the scouting survey on civic spaces conducted in the partner territories (see Deliverable 2.1 for details);
- Examples of meaningful ‘civic experiences,’ drawn from local expert interviews;
- An outline of the challenges and success factors for civic spaces, along with additional food for thought, highlighted in the Regional Boards organised in each territory.

Lastly, a comparative analysis of these findings presents the commonalities and specificities of the investigated territories, emphasising that, despite differences at many levels, civic spaces remain vital for bridging the policy-making process and citizens’ experiences, as well as giving voice to the unheard, enabling participation through various means, and reinforcing local economies.

Civic Spaces in the B.RIGHT SPACES territories

1. Civic Spaces in Catalonia

1.1 General Overview

Catalonia has a strong participatory culture, manifested at different levels and in different forms, being recognised for its successful participatory and deliberative democracy practices. These are recorded not only in the formal policymaking process but also in social, economic and cultural domains.

The consolidation of a shared and evolving culture of civic public space based on urban principles started in 1979, when a second Statute of Autonomy of Catalonia was established through a referendum that established local governance structures and granted significant autonomy to the region, with local councils regaining their power and responsibilities, lost under Franco's dictatorship (Casanovas, 2004). This process, together with the re-establishment of the Generalitat de Catalunya, shaped the further development of civic spaces. Nowadays, the region has a strong tradition of citizen participation and local democracy, with councils responsible for a wide range of services, including urban planning, education, and cultural activities.

Civil society plays a crucial role in Catalonia's civic spaces, particularly in shaping territorial identity and political processes. The discourse surrounding Catalan civil society has historically been associated with Catalan nationalism (Cramer, 2015). Indeed, research demonstrates how organised civil society has significantly influenced governmental decisions in political processes, including the 2014 consultation and 2017 referendum, utilising social networks and digital platforms to mobilise supporters and impact political agendas (Pascal, 2022).

Figure 1 Consultation and deliberation services on the GenCat portal: <https://governobert.gencat.cat/ca/participacio-ciutadana/>

A substantial body of research examines the development of civil society in Catalonia concerning the pro-independence and nationalist movements (Anderson, 2019; Miley, 2007). This topic remains

contentious, with ongoing debates about whether opposition to such movements constitutes a restriction of free speech and, consequently, indicates a narrowing of civic space (Negri & Pazderski, 2021; Kubiaczyk, 2018). Such debates highlight the ongoing tensions and complexities surrounding civic spaces and identity in Catalonia.

At the same time, civic participation has shown diverse trends in recent years. While there is a strong tradition of local participatory initiatives, manifested both offline and online, **the quality and extent of participation vary significantly across municipalities** (Borge, Colombo, & Welp, 2009). Larger cities tend to have more participatory experiences, both online and offline, influenced by factors such as population size, political party affiliation, and political context of the Municipality (Martí-Costa & Pybus, 2013) (Colombo, 2010). Civil society emerges as the most crucial explanatory factor of local civic participation (Font & Galais, 2011). In small municipalities, citizen participation is often focused on urban planning and informal processes (Serra, 2020). In public space management, **public consultations** have served not only as a participatory instrument but also as a modality of **conflict resolution** between parties and political legitimation while avoiding electoral costs (Casademont Falguera, Prieto-Flores, & Brugué Torruella, 2021).

Catalonian organisations possess substantial experience in **community management practices**. For instance, in the context of Barcelona, community-driven projects significantly contribute to transforming the city into a more democratic, sustainable, and inclusive environment. According to Xarxa d'Espais Comunitaris (XEC) (2021), a network of community spaces and projects focused on participatory and democratic management of public resources, the concept of community management contrasts with traditional top-down methods. Instead, it embraces horizontal decision-making, direct democracy, and local communities overseeing their own resources. As a result, community management equates to community empowerment, as it encourages local communities to take charge of their resources and spaces. The effectiveness of community management is further supported by an ecosystem of collaborators, including various networks, organisations, and public authorities. Another noteworthy network is Xarxa d'Economia Solidària (XES), which aims to promote social and solidarity economy practices and is also a project partner of B.RIGHT SPACES.

In the **cultural realm**, participation in public festivals, local cultural centres, and libraries contributes to the social cohesion of the community. For instance, attending public festivals or visiting the library engages individuals who may not typically consume culture or who are foreigners. Furthermore, such cultural participation aids in overcoming intergenerational barriers (Centre d'Estudis i Recursos Culturals, 2008). When studying participation in the Catalan region, the literature pays considerable attention to **youth participation**. The local structures for youth participation include local youth councils, youth committees, youth assemblies, municipal youth councils, and youth forums, with the latter two being administered by public authorities (Soler Masó, Novella Cámara, & Planas Lladó, 2015). Participation is also encouraged at a university level due to the University Students' Statute, which welcomed the creation of **students' councils**, which are valued venues for civic participation by students, even though the community aspect and the critical dimension of this experience could be improved through more relaxed regulations of the process (Jover Olmeda, López Martín, & Quiroga Uceda, 2011). The City Council of Barcelona, in particular, endeavours to promote active citizenship among **children and teenagers**, although a comprehensive policy in this area is lacking. Consequently, the City Council's efforts are more focused on education in participation and specific initiatives, which, while valuable, often have a limited temporal and geographical reach (Martín i Gómez & Truñó i Salvadó, 2016).

When it comes to **online participation**, in 2016, the City Council of Barcelona launched the participatory project decidim.barcelona, initially used for drafting the strategic plan of the city for

2016-2019. This resulted in increased transparency in the decision-making process, higher levels of participation and built momentum around key policy issues (Peña-López, 2019).

The platform allows citizens to propose, debate, and vote on municipal initiatives. It also facilitates participatory budgeting, where residents can decide how to allocate a portion of the city's budget. Since its launch, Decidim Barcelona has hosted numerous participatory processes, including urban planning projects, cultural initiatives, and social programmes. Moreover, being an open-source tool, it has been adopted by different social movements as a tool of internal participation. Its success, also evident in the increasing number of citizen proposals and initiatives and the engagement of new participant groups in policymaking, has inspired similar initiatives seeking to replicate Barcelona's experience in other municipalities (Borge & Padró-Solanet, 2023) and internationally (Garcia, Calleja-López, & Linares-Lanzman, 2023).

At the regional level, participation is facilitated through the [Participa Gencat platform](#), managed by the Catalan government. This platform enables citizens to take part in public consultations, provide feedback on government policies, and engage in online debates. It also includes tools for participatory budgeting and collaborative decision-making, among which are initiatives such as the development of the Catalan Climate Change Law and the participatory budgeting process for regional projects (Gencat, 2025). Nowadays, digital engagement has become an increasingly important aspect of civic participation in the region, harnessing technology to enhance citizen involvement in decision-making processes, public consultations, and community activities initiatives.

Good practices supported by the [Ajuntament de Barcelona](#) and the [Generalitat de Catalunya](#) aim to enhance participation and participative governance in community action associations. To achieve this, they can contract the services of social economy organisations that are well-rooted in the community. An example is [Community Balance](#), a tool that provides indicators to measure the community impact of projects. This tool was developed with public funding by a cooperative that collaborated with community spaces to create indicators based on their everyday practices. Now, the tool is open, allowing anyone to use or adapt it.

Catalonia's civic spaces are deeply rooted in **community values and social solidarity**, with a long tradition of collaboration between civil society and local administration. This has been strengthened, particularly in the last decade. An example is the increased support of the Barcelona City Council for the social and solidarity economy through programmes that enhance the professionalisation and financial autonomy of initiatives and foster cooperation between the administration and the social and solidarity-based economy (Cano-Hila & Pradel-Miquel, 2020). Since 2016, the Generalitat de Catalunya has supported the development of open government public policies and has promoted citizen participation as a cross-cutting strategy (Bermejo & Peña-López, 2020). The Generalitat de Catalunya is one of the managers of several networks of civic activities, including libraries, youth and senior centres, and civic centres, along with other local entities such as the deputations of all the provinces and the municipal councils. The ambition is to ensure that these centres are spaces of civic participation and social, political and democratic innovation.

This brief review highlights the specific characteristics of civic spaces in Catalonia, particularly their emphasis on community governance, social solidarity, and inclusivity. Citizen involvement is encouraged by public administration, which promotes mechanisms like participatory budgeting, participatory urban planning, and the Right to the City movements, all of which facilitate civic participation. The presented cases exemplify the new vision of the Administrations to develop a 'Good Government' and a quality 'Open Government' – where transparency is central. These institutions have been establishing tools and facilitating mechanisms to encourage citizen participation in institutional actions and promote community engagement through specific programmes, such as 'Urban Communalities' and 'ComunarESS' and, especially removing the

potential bureaucratic obstacles, as it is intended to be explored with the participation in the B.RIGHT SPACES project.

Further, an overview of the legal framework supporting civic spaces, the specific interpretation of the concept in the Catalan region, and examples gathered from expert interviews are presented.

1.2 The Legal Framework of Civic Spaces and Key Stakeholders

Civic spaces in Catalonia operate within a complex multi-level legal framework that encompasses Spanish national law, Catalan regional regulations, and European Union directives. At the national level, Spain has established comprehensive legislation covering transparency, public information access, and assembly rights, along with regulations governing public administration and assets, as well as natural heritage and biodiversity protection. At the regional level, Catalonia has developed its own specialised framework, including laws on citizen participation, public consultations, cultural heritage protection, urban planning, accessibility, and social economy initiatives. Additionally, the EU legislation related to human rights, data privacy and environmental protection also impacts civic spaces at a regional level.

At the legal foundation lies **the Spanish Constitution** of 1978, which establishes fundamental rights, including freedom of assembly and participation. Further, the region of Catalonia has its own regulations that shape civic spaces. Through the **Statute of Autonomy of Catalonia**, amended in 2006, the foundation for the region's self-governance was laid, stressing the citizens' rights to engage in political and social welfare. Specific provisions for public participation are set by **Law 19/2014 on transparency, access to public information and good governance**.

The management of civic spaces follows a decentralised model. While the Generalitat maintains responsibility for overall policy direction and funding allocation, local municipalities handle the day-to-day operation of these spaces. This arrangement reflects a strong commitment to decentralization, with an increasing emphasis on fostering collaboration between public institutions and community organisations. At the same time, this allows local municipalities to adopt their own regulations concerning civic spaces. An example is the **Regulation for the Use and Management of Civic Spaces of the Calafell City Council** (Reglament d'Ús i Gestió dels Espais Cívics de l'Ajuntament de Calafell). The regulation outlines the rules and procedures for the use and management of municipal civic spaces, aiming to promote citizen participation, social cohesion, and cultural, educational, and leisure activities. In the understanding of this document, civic spaces are municipal facilities intended for public use, supporting social, cultural, educational, and leisure activities that can serve as meeting points, support community activities, and promote citizen participation and associationism and are managed by public administration (Ajuntament de Calafell, 2019).

The ecosystem of civic spaces involves diverse **stakeholders**. The public sector is represented primarily by the Generalitat de Catalunya and local government authorities (town councils and county councils). The private and community sectors include Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) organisations, involved in the management and revitalisation of civic spaces, as well as the promotion of active participation; community associations, social movements, private companies, property owners, and citizens who actively participate in and use these spaces and act as agents of change. Additionally, expert interviews highlight self-managed cooperatives, popular culture groups (e.g., castellers and bastoners), school associations and traders. Overall, civic spaces in Catalonia

often involve a high degree of collaboration between all these diverse actors, including local government, community organisations, and private entities, reflecting a pluralistic approach to civic engagement. However, it is also stressed that many of these actors operate independently of institutional support [Expert Interviews 1, 2].

Several challenges remain for the development and management of civic spaces in the region. For example, even though in Catalonia, there are legal tools like the municipal charter that facilitate community management of public spaces, these are often underutilised or contested [Expert Interview 1]. The legal framework in Catalonia allows for the transfer of public spaces to community management, but this is often contested and requires strong community organisation. Moreover, the legal framework often favours privatisation and market-based solutions, making it difficult for community-managed spaces to thrive. The legal system is designed to protect private property, which often conflicts with community efforts to reclaim and manage public spaces. Although the region has been working on legal instruments to support community-managed spaces, there are still gaps, particularly in public procurement and funding mechanisms [Expert Interviews 1, 2].

Additional limitations include the necessity for clearer definitions of civic space concepts, enhancing accessibility, fostering community culture, addressing concerns about the legal and illegal use of facilities, streamlining regulations for third-sector entities, and strengthening citizen participation in decision-making processes.

Recent developments show promising evolution in this field. The forthcoming Social and Solidarity Economy Law aims to strengthen community initiatives and promote public-community partnerships. There is an increasing focus on sustainable development and social inclusion, with particular attention being paid to participatory urban planning and budgeting. These changes reflect a growing recognition of the importance of civic spaces in fostering community engagement and social cohesion.

1.3 The Common Understanding of Civic Spaces

The survey conducted by the Generalitat de Catalunya and XES collected 78 responses that contribute to understanding civic spaces among public administration, NGOs, social economy organisations, and both formal and informal community associations. Presented with the B.RIGHT SPACES working definition of civic spaces, the respondents were asked what elements they would add or modify in it. Approximately an equal number of responses were collected from participants representing public administration and social economy organisations, with around 30% of responses from each category. Other notable categories of respondents included civil society organisations and both formal and informal community groups.

Figures 3 and 4 present a visual representation of these answers in Catalan and translated into English, where the size of each word indicates the frequency of the word within the answers. The most common words in the text appear larger and more prominent, while less frequent words are smaller. This provides a quick overview of the main themes brought up by the respondents. The word clouds reflect that, aside from the key notion of 'civic space', the most dominant ideas revolve around the concepts of "community", "power", and "private". The emphasis on "**community**" resonates with the literature presenting case studies of civic spaces in Catalonia.

This is further clarified through the Expert Interviews. The experts prefer the term "community spaces" over "civic spaces," as they find the latter term repressive and tied to state structures. The term "civic" is often associated with state control, leading to a preference for "community" spaces

Example of civic space	Description	Specificity
<u>Ateneu L'Harmonia</u>	Community management in Sant Andreu de Palomar. Sociocultural equipment in Fabra i Coats.	Managed through partnership between administration and community.
<u>Ateneu Popular de Nou Barris</u>	The Ateneu Popular 9 Barris is a public socio-cultural space that operates according to the community management model, which was born from the neighbourhood occupation in 1977.	Rooted in community culture and community needs; Focus on inclusivity; Community self-management with institutional support.
<u>Ateneu Som de Salt</u>	One of the first community management projects in the Girona region, to put into practice the idea that citizens themselves are the ones who govern a public facility.	Community-managed; Focus on inclusivity.
<u>Bloc Quatre</u>	Cooperative Space from where to contribute to the development and socio-economic transformation of the city of Barcelona and the entire Catalan territory through raising awareness and promoting cooperativism, incubating and accelerating cooperatives, promoting inter-cooperation, local and international connections and alliances with other cultural, educational and business agents.	Community-managed; institutional support; focus on social and solidarity economy initiatives.
<u>Can Batlló</u>	A social and cultural facility located in different buildings, in the former textile factory of Can Batlló, in the Bordeta neighbourhood.	Private space turned into a community space; Balancing economic activity with addressing community needs.
<u>Can Fulgarolas</u>	Workshop on social, cultural and sustainable repairs	Rooted in community culture and community needs
<u>Can Masdeu</u>	The Vall de Can Masdeu is a community cooperation space rooted in Collserola where we shape habitable futures.	Emerged as a form of resistance and occupation.
<u>Can Sanpere</u>	Cultural centre in Premià de Mar.	Community-self management with institutional support; Focus on inclusivity.
<u>Casal del Pou de la Figuera</u>	Neighbourhood space with a community vocation, open to all participation for the creation and carrying out of activities.	Community-managed, operates under a civic management agreement but identifies as a community space.

Example of civic space	Description	Specificity
Casa Orlandai	The Casa Orlandai Cultural Association is a non-profit organisation, formed by the neighbourhood and groups linked to Sarrià, established to give life to the Casa Orlandai municipal facility.	Community-managed, focus on social and solidarity economy initiatives.
Decidim	Digital platform for citizen participation	Extension of physical community space
La Troca	A community space for ongoing training, a training project for young people and adults where we learn to develop as autonomous and critical individuals. It is a meeting and learning space, open to all young and adult residents of the Sants neighbourhood in Barcelona. It aims to respond to these shortcomings with a wide and varied offer and a new management model that gives sovereignty to the community.	Resilience despite economic instability
Nau Bostik	Socio-cultural facility located in the neighbourhood of La Sagrera.	Community-managed; Balancing economic activity with addressing community needs.
Xarxa de Dones Cosidores	A sewing group made up of women from diverse backgrounds who have come together as a community to become self-employed.	Resilience despite economic instability.

Table 1 Examples of Catalan Civic Spaces, identified through expert interviews

The **specificities of these civic spaces are not exclusive**. Aside from being fully community-managed, some community spaces achieve a balance between institutional support and community management, where public administration provides resources but does not control governance. The sustainability and self-management of the space without institutional control but with support and collaboration remain a potentially problematic issue [according to Expert Interview 2].

Examples such as Can Batlló, Can Sanpere, and Ateneu Nou Barris illustrate how Catalanian civic spaces navigate the balance between community autonomy and institutional support, often in the face of legal and political challenges [Expert Interview 1]. Nevertheless, Catalonia's civic spaces benefit from strong community networks and institutional recognition, particularly in urban areas like Barcelona.

Often, these spaces develop **income-generating activities** that contribute to the community, such as workshops or cultural events, without financial benefits necessarily being their main purpose. An example is Nau Bostik, which generates income through cultural events while maintaining its community focus. This is particularly important, as civic spaces in Catalonia often face challenges related to funding, but community-driven initiatives like Xarxa de Dones Cosidores demonstrate resilience and adaptability. Most importantly, the economic activity developed within the community shall align with its values [Expert Interview 2].

Although several of the listed community spaces target **vulnerable groups** specifically, inclusivity and safety are also achieved through community-driven processes, such as open assemblies and shared agendas. There is broad recognition in civic communities that inclusivity requires recognizing

diversity, facilitating participation, and addressing accessibility issues. Examples include cooperative universities and federations that promote inclusive practices [Expert Interview 2].

Civic spaces that emerge from **protest and resistance**, such as the occupation of Can Masdeu in Barcelona, are not seen as fundamentally different from other civic spaces but rather as responses to specific threats. Additionally, there is a growing movement to reclaim public spaces from privatisation and institutional control, with examples like Can Batlló, a factory turned community space. However, these resistance spaces often operate without institutional support.

Online civic spaces, such as the locally grown global participatory platform Decidim, are seen as extensions of physical community spaces. The experts emphasise the importance of physical meetings even in online communities.

1.5 Points for Further Reflection

Several points for reflection arise from the conclusions drawn from the expert interviews and the regional board meeting organised by XES and Generalitat de Catalunya in November 2024.

The meeting of the regional board highlighted the complexity of defining and managing civic spaces, particularly regarding social diversity, legal constraints, and the need for inclusivity. The discussions emphasised the importance of dynamic, accessible, and community-driven civic spaces while also identifying the challenges of legal reform, resource management, and citizen engagement. Addressing these issues necessitates a multifaceted approach that involves legal reforms, resource management strategies, and active citizen participation. Further research, dialogue, and collaboration among stakeholders will be vital to develop solutions that ensure civic spaces can fulfil their potential as hubs of social transformation and inclusion.

In the Catalan experience, **success factors** include strong community bonds, shared resources, and effective decision-making processes. The experts underscore the importance of documenting processes, enhancing collaboration, and learning from other communities, as well as, on a broader scale, educating and raising awareness about the significance of civic spaces. The expert interviews noted that the issue of civic spaces is not always prominent in public discourse, but there is growing recognition of their importance. In Catalonia, civic spaces are increasingly acknowledged in public discourse, especially in the context of social and solidarity economy initiatives. However, there remains a need for greater visibility and understanding.

2. Civic Spaces in Rome and Turin

2.1 General Overview

Non-profit Italian civil society organisations, commonly known as the **‘third sector’**, serve as intermediaries between the public and private spheres (Citroni, 2024). They lead and transform public participation by addressing community needs, repurposing traditional spaces, incorporating digital technologies, and expanding participatory methods through collaborative governance models. The activity of organised civil society is more institutionalised than in other European countries, with the process of institutionalisation commencing over thirty years ago, continuing to this day and impacting the structure of local welfare (ibid); (Fazzi, 2013).

Involving civic society in local governance practices in Italy is determined by a **‘collaborative governance’** approach, which encourages public administrations to involve citizens in developing, enhancing and reusing public goods to improve the quality of life in cities (Bartoletti & Faccioli, 2016). This is also reflected in continuous efforts to test and regulate **co-planning and co-programming** initiatives at the urban level (Arena & Bombardelli, 2022). Although these are top-down initiatives, such forms of civic collaboration increase opportunities for participation in decision-making and enhance the diversity of those involved, leading to more original, inclusive, informal, and individualised forms of civic activism focused on common goods (Bartoletti & Faccioli, 2016). Nevertheless, the shift toward more innovation in governance practices and the success of the collaborative governance models between institutions and citizens **varies by location**. Common challenges reported across studies, included bureaucratic obstacles, concerns about social exclusion, and tensions between grassroots independence and institutional oversight (Antonucci, Sorice & Volterrani, 2022).

Regarding the **impact of participatory practices**, a substantial body of research examines it through the lenses of urban planning and its effects on public spaces. Research on urban design incorporating community input shows that implementing participatory planning processes results in improved public space functionality and social cohesion (Antonucci, Sorice, & Volterrani, 2022). Moreover, the quality of public spaces is correlated with the outcomes of social integration (Marchigiani, 2018). Comparisons across cities revealed varying levels of success with participatory design processes, with some municipalities achieving higher levels of community engagement than others. When urban design incorporates community input, and public policies support inclusive access, civic spaces see increased usage (Antonucci et al. 2022). However, the research suggests that Italian cities still encounter considerable challenges in providing equitable access to quality public spaces throughout all neighbourhoods (Bianchi, Riga, Moscarelli, & Pileri, 2023).

Physical civic spaces are linked, within the Italian legal framework, to legislation concerning **‘civic use rights’** and the constitutional principle of **“horizontal subsidiarity”**, which primarily apply to collectively owned public goods and assets of public interest but may also encompass private spaces. These areas can exhibit the traits of common goods while simultaneously receiving specific, sometimes conflicting rights granted to particular communities under the system of ‘civic use rights’ (Casprini, Oppio, & Torrieri, 2023). In other cases, civic spaces are managed as urban commons through “Collaboration pacts”, specific agreements signed by the local public institutions and the community to cooperate for their care and regeneration under the “horizontal subsidiarity” principle (Arena, 2015). In both cases, these spaces are understood as common goods belonging to the citizens, when their use, management and governance involve the community (Masella, 2018).

Collaborative design processes and sustained community involvement in public processes have expanded to include both ad-hoc, direct action from civil society and structured approaches. Among these, consultations, participatory budgeting or public-private-non-profit partnerships are often implemented, also with the use of digital technologies (Antonucci, Sorice, & Volterrani, 2024).

At the same time, the shrinking of civic spaces is noticed in Italy as well, with increasing restrictions on civic freedoms originating from the domestic political government. Among the groups targeted by these restrictions are climate activists, sea-rescue NGOs, organisations defending migrants and asylum seekers and pro-Palestinian activists (Antonaki, 2024).

To conclude, traditional Italian public spaces are being repurposed through community initiatives and digital technologies, resulting in multipurpose civic spaces (Allegrini, 2016). Studies found that maintaining these new forms of civic engagement often required ongoing community participation and a careful balance between community initiatives and formal institutional support. While the reviewed research indicates civic organisations are changing how public participation occurs in Italian urban spaces, these changes appear to be highly dependent on local context and conditions.

2.2 Civic Spaces in the Metropolitan City of Rome

The capital city of Rome and its metropolitan territory are unique in the Italian context due to their geographical, historical, and governance factors, all leading to increasing inequalities over time. Civic activity in the city is characterized by forms of self-organisation, practices of reappropriating spaces, and shifting purposes and uses of places (Cellamare, 2023).

Additionally, one can observe an increase in active citizenship and mutualism in response to social needs that public authorities have not addressed, all aiming for an improved quality of life in urban areas. These activities can be self-managed and collaborative, and they sometimes take the form of informal, self-produced, territorial democratic practices (Cellamare, 2023).

A structure that has emerged in the territory of Rome to provide basic service infrastructure and serve as a space for the development of social, cultural, educational, sports, and entrepreneurship projects is referred to as '**civic centres**' or '**poli civici**' (Cellamare, 2022). These centres can include various initiatives spread throughout a district of the city, encompassing diverse social and physical spaces that can regenerate the territory in an integrated manner (Brignone, Olcuire, & Pontoriero, 2022).

An example that was first involved in the B.RIGHT SPACES field research and then visited in December 2024 is the community hub named '**POLEIS Polo Civico dell'Esquilino**'.

The '**poli civici**' or community hubs are formally established with the mission of combating poverty and social exclusion while promoting local development and economic initiatives, in alignment with the directive of the *Assemblea Capitolina* (City Council), which approved the corresponding regulatory framework in October 2024. Community hubs operate at the intersection of social and urban regeneration, serving as arenas for fostering and strengthening the political capacity of all individuals. These spaces play a vital role in building communities and reinforcing the social fabric.

In certain instances, community hubs build upon existing bottom-up and grassroots initiatives, integrating a formal structure that enables them to operate officially and gain access to available funding and other essential resources. This is exemplified by the *Quarticciolo* community hub. In the Quarticciolo district, known as a public housing suburb of Rome, the reappropriation of abandoned

public spaces is fostering the creation of a new social infrastructure (Nardis, Olcuire, & Fortuna, 2022). The B.RIGHT SPACES partners visited this civic space as well during the study visit in Rome.

As many citizens' groups have taken an active role in providing basic community services, it is common for formal and informal groups, such as neighbourhood non-profit organisations, grassroots political movements or even sports clubs, to claim publicly owned but unused spaces as common goods (Patti & Polyak, 2016). A strong tradition of occupying empty public buildings and green spaces exists, creating a parallel social infrastructure that addresses social needs not able to be met by public authorities. However, the squatting movement also serves as a catalyst for public authorities to adopt policy responses that address the social needs addressed by these organisations in the occupied spaces (Polyák, 2016).

Public authorities in Rome support civic spaces through various approaches, including collaborative governance models and co-planning practices. The city has implemented open government programmes since 2016, focusing on overcoming barriers to civic participation, such as institutional distrust and lack of digital skills (De Blasio, Colasanti, & Selva, 2020). Partnerships between municipalities and civil society are emerging as a new form of collaboration, bridging the gap between public and societal spheres and improving connections between the state and citizens (Viganò & Salustri, 2019). These partnerships contribute to innovative solutions for social risks and foster participatory policy-making. The aspects that require attention and ongoing support include the provision of financial, technical, and training resources to third-sector associations and other actors involved in managing civic spaces, along with strengthening collaboration among them.

Rome has also supported initiatives like solidarity purchase groups and migrants' social cooperatives, which address food insecurity, poverty reduction, and social integration (Bernaschi & Crisci, 2018). Nevertheless, more efforts could be dedicated to promoting inclusive participation across the entire society, with particular attention to the more vulnerable groups.

In terms of co-planning practices, a case study of Schuster Park in Rome documented positive results from tactical urbanism and co-design approaches in a previously underutilised area (Magarò, Mariani, & Trulli, 2024). Similar findings are reported by the urban gardening initiative in Parco delle Energie, which challenged traditional planning perspectives and fostered a co-creative form of public space management (Certomà, Chelleri, & Notteboom, 2020).

Finally, the metropolitan city of Rome is using digital citizen consultation tools in various ways. Certain subjects are decentralised to the municipalities, which promotes consultations on neighbourhood issues and broader topics, such as the urban space, safety and insecurity, civic and cultural innovation centres, and others, for city-wide consultations (Antonucci, Sorice, & Volterrani, 2024). However, digital tools could be more exploited to facilitate participation, communication and the management of civic spaces.

2.4 Civic Spaces in Turin

The city of Turin has developed a complex governance network involving different levels of government and diverse stakeholders, leading to better urban innovation performance compared to other Italian cities (Dente, Spada, & Bobbio, 2005). The city has a long history of civic participation, especially in urban regeneration and social innovation policies.

In particular, local dialogue and community engagement started at the end of the nineties, with the **Progetto Speciale Periferie** (Outskirts Special project) set up, which later (in 2001) became **Settore Periferie** (Outskirts Department). Key elements of this project were an integrated approach, citizens'

participation, procedural and organisational innovation, identity and sense of belonging, improvement, and development opportunities. It developed through different urban regeneration programmes that culminated, between 2007 and 2013, in forming eight community centres called **Case del Quartiere** (Neighbourhood Houses), located in various districts of the city and which are constantly evolving to better respond to the needs of local communities. These Neighbourhood Houses comprise a network of multi-purpose hubs that work together to support community cooperation and civic engagement. Aside from being places of active participation, encouraging people to take part in different forms of active citizenship, volunteering and cultural activities, they are also social infrastructures where people look for and experiment with new ways of planning and managing social welfare policies and activities, developing proximity-based networks and finding collective solutions to common needs. Deeply rooted in the territory, each of the eight houses works independently as a multi-functional community hub located in different areas of the city. Additionally, there are also centres of interculturalism, which they harness as a social, cultural, and political driver for civil society activities (Caponio & Donatiello, 2017).

The active collaboration and citizen involvement in the planning processes, recognised as best practices for creating more livable and inclusive cities, are embraced by Torino within the framework of its 'smart city' policy (Dezi, Pisano, Pironti, & Papa, 2018). The collaboration between public authorities and civil society organisations is well established, with openness towards the use of collaborative platforms for public-private interactions for social innovation (De Filippi, Coscia, & Cocina, 2017). Online consultations were also adopted by the public administration of Turin, which consulted inhabitants concerning the metropolitan strategic plan (Antonucci, Sorice, & Volterrani, 2024). Attention is drawn, however, to the autonomy of public administration in deciding on various participatory projects, even when the aim is to empower local communities. In the case of San Salvario neighbourhood, it is claimed that these facilitated experiences align with the public agenda (Bolzoni, 2019).

Another example of Turin's urban transformation is the enhancement of one of its most industrialised areas – the "Barriera di Milano" – where cultural initiatives have redefined the urban landscape as a civic space. A case study of this experience illustrates that community-driven initiatives, which are self-sustaining and economically viable, can foster a sense of belonging within the community, even among marginalised groups, and support local collective action (Salone, Bonini Baraldi, & Pazzola, 2017).

A complementary good practice in transforming a 'space' into 'place' is noted in one of the Residual Areas Projects, a programme managed by the Municipality that involved co-designing an urban public area with the participation of multiple stakeholders. This project demonstrates that a bottom-up, co-design approach engaging citizens, users, mediators, and planners can effectively redesign and revitalise neglected urban spaces, thereby enhancing their usability (Salice, 2016). An interdisciplinary approach with resident engagement is highlighted as essential to increase the usability of public spaces in Torino (Chiodi, 2014).

Overall, Turin is an innovative and supportive city for civic spaces, hosting one of the best practices recognised at the national level: the Neighbourhood Houses, which hold strategic importance for the Municipality and are currently backed by both local and regional authorities. Moreover, there are other projects and initiatives to promote civic spaces, including interdisciplinary approaches and resident engagement.

The most significant weakness, according to the Turin Municipality, is the structural financial crisis and the shortage of human resources that Italian public administrations can allocate to social innovation policies.

2.5 The Legal Framework of Civic Spaces

The legal framework that applies to civic spaces in Italy at the national level is characterized by a combination of constitutional principles and national laws. Regional regulations further concretise the framework affecting civic spaces.

2.5.1 Legislation at National Level

At its core, Article 118.4 of **the Italian Constitution** establishes the principle of horizontal subsidiarity, which supports “autonomous citizens' initiatives, either as individuals or in association, to carry out activities of general interest”. This principle is foundational for the promotion of civic spaces and citizen participation. Unfortunately, there is currently no national law that permits the enforcement of the last paragraph of Article 118, which affects the extent and instances of actual citizen participation in the management and planning of government actions.

The **Third Sector Code**, adopted in 2017, outlines the framework for the activity of the third sectors, as well as the tools for collaboration between public administrations and third sector bodies, including provisions for co-programming, co-planning, and covenants for cultural heritage, as detailed in Articles 55, 56, and 71. These are complemented by **Ministerial Guidelines 72/2021**, which emphasise the importance of civic spaces and citizen participation.

Additionally, the **Public Contract Code** (Legislative Decree 36/2023) includes provisions for public-private partnerships and public debate, which are relevant for the development and management of civic spaces. In the educational sector, the **School Plan 2020/2021** and **2021/2022** promotes subsidiarity and educational co-responsibility through 'Educational community agreements,' which can include the development of civic spaces within educational contexts.

Additionally, the **National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)**, funded through the EU's Next Generation programme, includes funding for the creation and redevelopment of civic spaces,

However, despite this diverse basis for supporting civic spaces, Italian legislation lacks a clear definition of "civic space" due to the absence of a national standard. This can create ambiguity and complicate the identification and regulation of these realities.

2.5.2 Regional Legislation affecting Civic Spaces

Italian municipalities enjoy a degree of autonomy in developing regulations and policies to support civic spaces. However, this autonomy is constrained by national and regional legislation, which can result in inhomogeneity and fragmentation at the territorial level.

At the regional level, the development of civic spaces in the metropolitan city of Rome and Turin is influenced by **Lazio Regional Law 10/2019** and **Piedmont Regional Law 14/03/2024**, n. 5, respectively. These legislative documents refer, among other things, to the shared administration of common goods and promote horizontal subsidiarity, providing forms of institutional participation for citizens and associations, thus overcoming the legislative vacuum at the national level. Locally, both cities have developed specific regulations to support civic spaces.

2.5.3 *Legislative Framework for Supporting Civic Spaces in the Metropolitan City of Rome*

In Rome, one of the key documents is the **Statute of Rome Capital**, approved in March 2013. This statute incorporates principles of subsidiarity and citizen participation, with a dedicated chapter on "Popular Participation and Protection of Civic Rights". It establishes the foundation for involving citizens in governance and decision-making processes, emphasising the importance of civic engagement in the management of public and common goods.

In May 2023, the **Rome Regulation for the Shared Administration of Common Material and Intangible Goods (2023)** was adopted. This regulation is a significant step forward in promoting collaborative governance. It introduces tools such as Collaboration Agreements (both ordinary and complex) to facilitate partnerships between citizens and the administration in managing common goods. Additionally, it establishes the Active Citizens Forum, a body tasked with ensuring the full implementation of the regulation and fostering active citizen involvement in governance. The regulation is built on the principles of subsidiarity and participation, aiming to create a more inclusive and collaborative approach to managing civic spaces.

More recently, on October 24, 2024, the City Council of Rome approved the **Proposal for the Regulation of Integrated Civic Centres for Mutualism**. This regulation focuses on the creation and management of civic centres for mutualism and integration in various Roman neighbourhoods. It aims to promote forms of sharing and territorial governance driven by citizens' organisations, further strengthening the role of civic spaces in fostering community engagement and social cohesion.

In addition to these formal regulations, Rome has implemented several local initiatives and projects supported by municipal funding and policies. For example, as part of the PNRR, Rome is developing 68 **Civic Centres for Culture and Innovation** (30 in Rome and 38 in the Metropolitan City). These centres aim to promote cultural and social innovation while enhancing community participation. The city is also working on **Neighbourhood Laboratories** in areas such as Corviale, Tor Bella Monaca, and S. Maria della Pietà, which follow participatory approaches to urban redevelopment. Furthermore, Rome has activated 7 **civic centres for mutualism and integration** in various neighbourhoods, funded by the municipal budget, to support local governance and community-driven initiatives.

Overall, the metropolitan city of Rome is working to create a more inclusive and collaborative approach to governance and community engagement through a combination of formal regulations and local initiatives and projects. These efforts are part of a broader strategy to enhance the role of civic spaces in promoting social cohesion and democratic participation.

2.5.4 *Legislative Framework for Supporting Civic Spaces in Turin*

Similar to Rome, the legal and regulatory framework governing civic spaces in Turin is influenced by a mix of national, regional, and local legislation, along with specific initiatives and projects. First, national principles of subsidiarity and collaboration are articulated in the Italian Constitution and the Third Sector Code. Second, at the regional level, there are Piedmont's laws regarding the shared administration of common goods.

Locally, Turin has developed specific regulations and initiatives to support civic spaces.

Turin's Local Regulation on Urban Commons (2016) is a key piece of legislation that allows for a deeper involvement of urban actors—citizens, civil society, private actors, and knowledge institutions—in the care and regeneration of urban commons.

In 2014, a national debate on urban commons regulation began in Bologna and quickly spread to several major Italian cities, including Turin. In 2016, the Turin City Council, demonstrating its strong commitment to civic engagement and urban regeneration, issued a local regulation on urban commons. This regulation, which allows for the deeper involvement of urban actors—citizens, civil society, private entities, and knowledge institutions—in the care and regeneration of urban commons, has been a significant step forward. The aim is to encourage and sustain new collaborative forms of dialogue with civil society regarding the management of public goods and the provision of collective services by establishing **Pacts of Collaboration** between citizens' organisations and public administration. The implementation of this regulation was further enhanced by the **Co-City project** under the Urban Innovative Actions Programme framework, which aimed to address urban poverty and social fragmentation by promoting civic participation in the care of urban commons and the creation of proximity welfare services. Today, the city of Turin has more than **60 Collaboration Pacts signed**.

Additionally, the **Resolution of the Turin City Council** (12 October 2020, no. 75) concerns the Reform of Decentralization and Participation and aims to create spaces for interaction between the administration and citizens. It supports the activation and management of co-design processes in specific neighbourhoods, further promoting civic spaces.

The Memorandum of Understanding between the City of Turin and the Neighbourhood Houses (2024) formalises the collaboration between the public administration and the Neighbourhood Houses. This agreement aims to consolidate and develop these civic spaces as strategic resources for public policies. Moreover, the document states the agreement on creating new Neighbourhood Houses and the support in evaluating their social impact.

The **Torino Social Impact Platform** represents the local ecosystem for social innovation and aims to promote social impact through collaborative, inclusive, and sustainable economic practices. It supports the development of civic spaces as part of its broader mission.

2.6 The Common Understanding of Civic Spaces

Ninety-seven responses were collected from Italy for the survey examining perceptions of civic spaces in local territories, conducted by CSV Lazio, Associazione PARSEC, and the Municipality of Turin during the initial phase of the B.RIGHT SPACES project. The majority of these responses (57%) are from civil society organisations, non-governmental organisations, and non-profit entities. Social economy organisations and entrepreneurship groups constitute the next largest category of respondents, followed by public administration and various types of formal or informal community groups.

As shown in Figure 5 (English translation – Figure 6), the three key terms most frequently mentioned by respondents to nuance their understanding of 'civic spaces', aside from 'civic spaces', are '**public**', '**citizen**', and '**social**'. This reflects the debate surrounding the fine line between civic spaces and public spaces, as noted in the academic literature, as well as the experiences of respondents in using and managing civic spaces.

Additionally, one can categorize these and other frequently used terms such as “**democratic**”, “**collective**”, “**administration**”, “**community**”, and “**action**” within a participatory democracy framework for civic spaces, emphasising a social and community focus.

2.7 Civic Spaces in Practice in Rome

Associazione PARSEC and CSV Lazio conducted three expert interviews to understand the specificities of civic spaces in the metropolitan city of Rome. This section summarizes the key insights from these discussions and highlights some prominent examples of local civic spaces, identified by the experts or visited by the consortium partners during a study visit in Rome.

These examples can be gathered mostly under the umbrella term of ‘*poli civici*’, although other forms of experimental aggregation supported by public policies such as Neighbourhood laboratories, urban regeneration projects, open and participatory schools, and others, exist.

The common characteristic of these Civic Spaces concerns the use of common spaces to generate connections between: "doing" (services, interventions, events, protests, etc.), the interception of needs, the direct protagonism of citizens and the redevelopment of social ties. The quality of the spaces that guarantees the functioning of this mechanism is "being accessible to all".

Poli civici are community-driven spaces that aim to bring together various actors—associations, citizens, and institutions—to address local needs and foster social cohesion. They serve as hubs for social, cultural, and economic activities, often filling gaps left by institutional failures. They are multi-functional, addressing a wide range of issues such as poverty, youth engagement, local economic development, and cultural exchange. Importantly, they shouldn’t be perceived only as physical spaces but also as relational spaces that foster social ties and community resilience.

A key feature of poli civici is their emphasis on inclusivity and participation. Decisions are often made through citizens' assemblies or participatory processes, ensuring that the community has a direct say in the activities and projects undertaken.

The interviewees noted that the topic of civic spaces is not widely discussed in Italian public discourse, particularly in traditional and social media. It is the local, alternative media like *comune.info*, which provides a counter-narrative to mainstream media and reports on social transformations and civic initiatives. Increased awareness and advocacy are needed to emphasise the significance of poli civici in building democratic and inclusive communities.

There is a push to expand the number of poli civici across Rome, aiming to establish two per Municipality. This expansion requires institutional support and a commitment to participatory planning and community involvement.

While the focus of the experts interviewed is on physical spaces, there is recognition of the potential role of online civic spaces in facilitating communication and coordination. However, physical presence and face-to-face interactions are seen as essential for building trust and social ties.

Example 1 - Polo dell'Esquilino per l'Innovazione Sociale

The Polo dell'Esquilino per l'Innovazione Sociale – POLEIS is a *polo civico*, that is a civic space situated in the Esquilino district of Rome, bringing together various associations dedicated to urban marginality, social inclusion, and community needs. This space promotes interaction and exchange among the different associations, addressing issues that range from poverty to youth support, and aims to rebuild social ties in a district that has lost much in its social cohesion over the past 50 years. Thus, it acts as a nurturing environment for community cohesion and social reconstruction [Expert Interview 3]. It was highlighted as a best practice from Rome in all three expert interviews.

The governance of this space is democratic, with every proposal from Polo Civico Esquilino first evaluated in a citizens' assembly, ensuring that the community holds a direct voice in the activities and projects undertaken. The Polo Civico primarily uses physical meetings, with occasional online meetings for coordination. Social media is used for communication but it can also easily transform into space for conflict and deconstruction of civic actions [Expert Interview 4].

Moreover, the Polo Civico offers resources and support to its associations. For example, it has a social communicator who works to engage the local market and community, fostering a sense of shared purpose. In conflictual situations, it can serve as both a space for protest and constructive actions. For example, during a protest, young activists connected with the Polo Civico Esquilino, which provided organisational support and helped channel their energy into constructive actions [Expert Interview 4].

The civic space collaborates with the Municipality of Rome on urban and logistical planning, emphasising the needs of both associations and citizens. Thus, the space can be seen as a co-designed environment where local associations and institutions work together. Balance is achieved through dialogue and shared projects, such as the Festival of Liberazioni [Expert Interview 4]. Even when associations from the civic space have a conflictual relationship with the authorities, such as the squatting movement 'Spin Time', which is the largest community centre in Italy, unexpected interventions from other social actors acknowledging its social importance – such as the Pope in this case – can mitigate the situation (Verdu, 2023).

The economic contribution of the space to the community is seen through the Esquilino market, where local businesses and social initiatives interact. Moreover, small businesses like bakeries and restaurants in the Esquilino district can contribute to social aggregation and community-building.

This civic space is also viewed as an area that uses culture as a tool for fostering relationships and combating social issues such as stigma and racism. The Cinema Apollo, located in Esquilino, is referenced by one expert as a potential site for a civic space that could function as a cultural, economic, and social centre for the multi-ethnic community in the area [Expert Interview 5]. The space could be used not just as a cinema but also as a co-working space and a hub for local economic activities, such as smart working for residents who want to work closer to home. Nevertheless, in the experts' view, the development of the Cinema Apollo as a civic space should be driven by the needs and desires of the local community, rather than being imposed by the administration [Expert Interview 5].

Example 2 - Polo civico Quarticciolo

This civic hub is described as a self-organised space that emerged from grassroots efforts, rooted in the local community of the social housing district of Quarticciolo and its needs. According to [Expert Interview 4], it can be considered a typical example of self-organised space that often arises in response to institutional neglect or policy failure. Therefore, it has a more conflictual relationship with public authorities rather than a collaborative one.

One of its core facilities, and the one that forms the basis of the civic space, is its popular gym, which serves not only as a sports venue but also as a social stronghold in the neighbourhood.

Additionally, the *centri sociali* in Quarticciolo are mentioned as important spaces of protest and social activism that have historically been associated with opposition. These spaces have played an important role in providing a voice for marginalised groups and fostering social activism. At the same time, the withdrawal of the welfare state from the neighbourhood – including the closing of schools, libraries, and swimming pools – resulted in the informal delegation of responsibilities from public institutions to the community, leading to a new social and civic reality that developed in synergy with existing resources.

In spite of attempts by the Municipality to engage, such as organising events and initiatives at the Quarticciolo civic centre (e.g., the annual boxing event), the space is in a precarious state. Although there may be a willingness from authorities to collaborate with conflictual civic spaces when they address genuine community needs, without proper resource allocation and fulfilling the role of the welfare state, the civic spaces are at risk.

Example 3 - Polo Civico Roma Nord

Located in the Bastogi and Monte Spaccato neighbourhoods, this civic space was established recently with municipal support, focusing on agriculture and local economic development. It works closely with the Coraggio cooperative to manage public lands and promote community projects and local entrepreneurship, with the aim to revitalise local economy.

The polo civico Roma Nord is also involved in the management of public space, such as the Cassia 22 hectares project, which is an important agricultural initiative. Additionally, the Borghetto San Carlo project, a small architectural jewel in the area, is being renovated to host municipal offices and activities of the Coraggio cooperative. This project is seen as an example of how civic spaces can be recomposed to serve multiple community needs, even in less fortunate neighbourhoods that lack large green spaces or other resources [Expert Interview 5].

Figure 6 Some pictures of the Quarticciolo community hub, taken during the B.RIGHT SPACES visit (December 2024)

Example 4 - Cooperativa Sociale Garibaldi

The Cooperativa Sociale Garibaldi is highlighted as an example of a successful civic space that combines social agriculture with economic autonomy. The cooperative works with families of children with severe autism, providing them with opportunities to engage in agricultural activities and run a small social restaurant. This model allows families to stay together and avoid placing their children in residential care facilities.

An interviewee notes that the cooperative has faced significant challenges, including political opposition and judicial interventions, but has managed to persist and thrive. The cooperative is seen as a model for how civic spaces can generate income while also providing social value to the community [Expert Interview 5].

Example 5 - Rete delle Banche del Tempo

Rete delle Banche del Tempo (Time Banks Network) is an example of a civic space that has been revitalised by the Municipality. Time banks are community-based systems where people exchange services using time as a currency, fostering social cohesion and mutual support.

The Time Banks Network has been an important tool for community engagement and social inclusion, particularly in areas where traditional services are lacking. The network is seen as a way to rebuild trust and strengthen community ties.

The examples above provide an overview of just a few civic spaces in Rome, ranging from institutionally supported to co-managed, self-organised, and community-managed. While these represent different stages of development and recognition, they encounter some common challenges. Among these is the weakness of local institutions, which often fail to provide adequate support or recognise the importance of civic spaces [Expert Interview 5]. For example, The PNRR has allocated funds without a clear vision, leading to ineffective use of resources for civic spaces [Expert Interview 3]. Bureaucratic and administrative hurdles present an additional challenge. Excessive institutional control risks suffocating bottom-up initiatives [Expert Interview 4]. Third, the fragmentation of civil society and the lack of coordination among different actors can hinder the effectiveness of their activities, as well as their legitimate recognition as vital stakeholders in the city's democratic landscape. Moreover, many associations struggle to have the material and knowledge resources to ensure continuous, successful citizen engagement [Expert Interview 5]. Lastly, the reduction of social spaces due to urban policies is a major barrier to the consolidation of civic spaces, as many public spaces have been lost in the city due to urban development, leading to a lack of places where people can gather and interact [Expert Interview 4].

2.8 Civic Spaces in Practice in Turin

The Municipality of Turin conducted two expert interviews to better understand the local nuances and specifics of civic spaces. The experts provided insights into the concept of civic spaces, their role in democracy, and the challenges and opportunities they face.

Both interviewees defined civic spaces as **physical and virtual spaces** that promoted community engagement, policy reform and social transformation. They can be **institutional or self-organised**, and both forms are equally important for democracy and community participation [Expert Interviews 6, 7]. However, self-organised spaces often need advocacy to achieve concrete results [Expert Interview 7].

The topic of civic spaces in Turin is not widely present in mainstream **public discourse**, but it is occasionally covered in specialised media. It is actively debated among experts, practitioners, and civil society organisations. Traditional media tend to focus on the physical aspects of civic spaces, such as the repurposing of unused public assets, while social media discussions are more insular and confined to specialised communities. In Turin, the debate is more localised and focuses on how civic spaces can contribute to urban regeneration, social innovation, and community development. Advocacy efforts by networks of civic spaces aim to influence public policy and secure recognition for these spaces at both the local and national levels. However, there is a need to move beyond the innovation narrative and focus on ensuring the continuity and sustainability of successful civic space initiatives. A solution in this regard, implemented by the Municipality of Turin, is the Memorandum of Understanding between the city administration and the neighbourhood houses, further described below.

According to expert interview 6, public bodies sometimes exhibit some rigidity in acknowledging that social enterprises can contribute to the local economy by combining business and social objectives. This is particularly evident in the context of the Piedmont Regional Law on the Third Sector. Although this law recognises the possibility for nonprofit organisations to enter into agreements to reuse public properties for socio-cultural purposes, it does not include social enterprises as eligible entities for such agreements.

The presence of public agencies that operate at the intermediary level between public administration and the community (such as the Urban Committee in Turin and [Hangar](#) at the level of Piedmont Region) can facilitate the connection between the two stakeholders, as they are closely linked with local communities and also experiment on behalf of public organisations [Expert Interview 6].

Both experts recognise that civic spaces can emerge from **protest** or **resistance** to institutional policies. They can also emerge from campaigns that pressure political authorities. Examples include civic mutualism (e.g., Trame di quartiere in Catania) and community welfare initiatives that collaborate with public administrations to provide social services, although these examples are not particular to Turin.

The main example of civic space in Turin, highlighted in the expert interviews, is the Rete delle Case del Quartiere, presented in the general overview (section 2.4) and further described below.

Example 1 – [Rete delle Case del Quartiere](#)

Rete delle Case del Quartiere is a non-profit network of eight “Case del Quartiere” (Neighbourhood Houses) co-designed in 2012 by the Municipality of Turin and different actors of the third sector to promote innovative social enterprises as a means of mitigating the risk of social exclusion. They exemplify how civic spaces can serve as hubs for social innovation and community empowerment in urban settings like Turin. This policy has been fostered by the public administration and co-designed with the Compagnia di San Paolo Foundation, the main philanthropic organization in the north-west region of Italy. Furthermore, this foundation has signed an agreement with the City to provide financial support for the eight Neighbourhood Houses.

Figure 7 Map of Turin with the 8 Case del Quartiere

These multi-purpose and multi-stakeholder centres support activities aimed at job creation, urban regeneration, and socio-cultural initiatives (Commission, 2022). Their success is achieved through public-private partnerships and through a collaborative governance model between the public administration, non-profit associations and the local community.

An example is [Cascina Roccafranca](#), which was the firstly designed Neighbourhood House, where the Turin Municipality collaborates with over 20 non-profit organisations, ensuring that the space is managed by a Foundation in a way that benefits the community while maintaining a strong connection with public institutions. Moreover, the city has employees who works in a detached capacity at the Cascina.

The Neighbourhood Houses are structured to be inclusive and to encourage participation from diverse groups within the community. They often involve co-designing activities and services with the beneficiaries, ensuring that the spaces meet the needs of the local population. They can include cultural and educational events, well-being courses, information desks, meetings, workshops and others. Further, an online dimension could be integrated into these activities to increase engagement, particularly of younger populations.

Although the space benefits from mainly philanthropic foundation funding, commercial activities are crucial in ensuring the economic sustainability of Neighbourhood Houses. These activities, such as cafes, restaurants, and space rentals, help cover operational expenses. They are also spaces of inclusivity, as some Neighbourhood Houses include restaurants that provide job opportunities for disadvantaged individuals or shops that promote the circular economy.

According to one of the interviewed experts [6], the Neighbourhood Houses are an example that aligns with most of the characteristics outlined in the B.RIGHT SPACES definition of civic spaces. These spaces are designed to foster community engagement, social cohesion, and local development while promoting active citizenship and urban regeneration.

Another interesting nuance of civic spaces in Turin is their obvious capacity to influence adjacent public spaces, enhancing civic participation and community engagement. For example, the [Via Baltea Community Hub](#) has worked on the pedestrianization of the adjacent street ([Baltea Lido project](#)) and [Imbarchino](#), demonstrating how civic spaces can care for and improve their surrounding public areas. Interestingly enough, such civic spaces mentioned above although not comprised within the 8 Neighbourhood Houses, still perform exactly as community spaces for public participation. That is to say that the panorama of civic spaces in Turin is diverse and vibrant and goes beyond the Neighbourhood Houses model.

Two essential elements for the **success of civic spaces** can be highlighted based on the barriers and limitations highlighted by the interviewed experts, as well as from the practical examples from the city of Turin.

First, coherent monitoring and evaluation activities are needed in civic spaces to enhance understanding of their significance and public nature, as well as to help secure funding. Second, educational activities and training are essential for both public administrations, to better comprehend their complexity and specificities, and for civil society organisations and other civic space actors, to strengthen their capacities and sustainability.

2.9 Points for Further Reflection

This section presents several key concerns and additional action points raised by the Italian Regional Board, organised by CSV Lazio, PARSEC, and the Municipality of Turin in November 2024, concerning civic spaces both nationally and specifically in the cities of Rome and Turin. The aim is not to summarise the discussion but to complement the findings presented in other sections of this document report.

In Rome and Turin, civic spaces often emerge as independent community initiatives that gradually undergo institutionalisation processes. These spaces typically start with communities taking ownership of the initiative, maintaining autonomy from institutions while empowering themselves through horizontal subsidiarity. This allows them to gain power and protagonism in their relationships with public administrations.

As communities become more active participants, their relationship with the administration evolves; however, this dynamic can present challenges. For example, services offered in civic spaces, which complement public services, may become low-cost outsourcing options for public administrations. Workers in these spaces sometimes feel pressured to accept requests from authorities, which can distort the relationship and undermine the ability of civic spaces to fulfill their distinctive role. Philanthropic foundations and other influential societal actors (such as the atypical intervention of the Vatican in the case of Spin Time in Rome) can help bridge the gap and resolve conflicts between public entities and local initiatives. Moreover, philanthropic entities, including foundations, can support experimental projects that may be recognised by institutions later. These bodies often act as intermediaries between policies and local initiatives.

A key prerequisite for the emergence of civic spaces is the presence of civic activism in the related territories. This is seen in the practice of Neighbourhood Houses in Turin. Where such activism is

lacking, according to the interviewed experts, public entities are responsible for creating the necessary conditions for the development of civic spaces. However, the issue of fragmented political interventions arises—should these interventions be integrated into broader urban policies or not? Integrating civic spaces as a priority within a common territorial legal framework could address the fragmentation of sectoral policies and the absence of a shared, strategic vision for the development of these spaces.

Additionally, social and civic actors often do not engage in dialogue, which makes it challenging to unite, think collectively, and share civic spaces or common visions for their territory. The regional board identifies this as a cultural issue that must be addressed to help these realities transcend their individual interests and foster the creation of civic spaces.

3. Civic Spaces in Torres Vedras

3.1 General Overview

Recent studies indicate that civic spaces in Portugal are evolving, albeit with some challenges. While no clear definition of ‘civic spaces’ is formally established in the national legal or political framework, there is a growing interest in participatory dynamics and solidarity initiatives, along with increased civil society involvement in areas such as housing, transport, and ecology. The Portuguese administration is adopting a **human rights-based approach** to public services, placing citizens, their needs, and their involvement at the heart of these services. However, despite public administration's efforts to foster greater involvement through innovative governance mechanisms, participation remains relatively modest compared to other European countries (Fernandes, Teles, Chamusca, & Seixas, 2020). The post-COVID-19 effects, demographic challenges, digital divide, and overall low levels of public participation present obstacles to the success of the participatory approach of the administration (OECD, 2023). Bureaucratic hurdles and corruption are two additional barriers that can impede or slow the success of civic spaces [Expert Interview 9].

The Portuguese civil society bridges delivery gaps in public services, holds public institutions accountable and advocates for human rights (OECD, 2023). Their support for bottom-up initiatives also provides space for collective action, challenging the lack of interest, trust, and awareness regarding the decision-making process (Mota & Ataíde, 2023). One of the biggest challenges faced by civil society is **the lack of financial sustainability**.

Online public participation is observed as a general trend, occurring informally through the sharing of news on social media and formally through participation in online voting (Quintanilha, 2018). Online tools are used for public mobilisation, particularly around protests (Babo, 2017), mainly through social media engagement (Amaral, 2020). It is also a way to bring youth closer to the decision-making process, as informal online participation on social media correlates with higher formal civic participation offline (Dias Fonseca, 2019). Furthermore, the online environment serves as a space for civic agency when youth are already involved in formalised, offline civic actions (ibid).

The general trends are also reflected in the dynamic of Torres Vedras' civic spaces.

In recent years, the Municipality of Torres Vedras has implemented a wide range of programmes and initiatives aimed at revitalising public spaces, promoting civic engagement, and ensuring that civic spaces are accessible and inclusive for all residents. This evolution highlights the growing recognition of the importance of civic spaces in fostering community well-being and democratic participation.

The evolution of Torres Vedras' policies towards civic spaces reflects a shift from basic infrastructure development in the post-revolution period to a more comprehensive approach that emphasises public participation, social inclusion, and sustainable urban development.

The latter is connected to the broader context of urban growth across Portugal and, more specifically, the Oeste Region, which extends northwest of the Lisbon Metropolitan area. The proximity to the capital city of Lisbon and the relatively lower housing prices have resulted in an increasing population in Torres Vedras over the past few decades, creating both challenges and opportunities for urban development (Barreira, Amado, Santos, Andraz, & Guimaraes, 2021); (Gomes, Banos, Abrantes, Rocha, & Schläpfer, 2020).

Civic spaces are connected to urban public spaces and their projection, architecture, and use (Coelho, 2015). The design of open spaces around urban mobility infrastructure presents opportunities for social appropriation and environmental performance, with waterway connections generally offering better social interactions compared to road/rail connections (Figueiredo, 2020). For example, the urban square of the Arts and Creativity Centre of Torres Vedras was conceived as an outdoor events hall mainly used for events and socialising (Fernandes, 2025) but also included a social interaction and exchange component in its agenda (Centro de artes e criatividade Torres Vedras, 2025).

The emphasis on smart cities as a mode of urban development, which involves knowledge sharing among stakeholders and collaboration to co-create solutions to urban challenges, has also steered Torres Vedras toward engaging civic society in the urban innovation process to establish a sustainable, attractive, and inclusive urban ecosystem (Selada, 2017). Participatory budgeting has been implemented in the Municipality since 2015, with the decisions being taken by the population, even though the process is perceived as a way of gaining legitimacy for political decisions (Santos, Batel, & Gonçalves, 2019). Aside from governance, other areas of collaborative policy making include environment, mobility and quality of life (Lopes & Oliveira, 2017). The Municipality also supports projects aimed at promoting social participation and urban regeneration, particularly in areas characterised by social segregation, poor accessibility and degraded urban spaces (Nascimento, Alves, & Sousa, 2021).

Additionally, the close relationship between culture and public space in Portugal is also reflected in Torres Vedras. The local government recognises the importance of creativity and innovation in driving economic growth, fostering community engagement, and enhancing the quality of life for its residents (Município de Torres Vedras, 2025). In its commitment to supporting and promoting the creative sector as part of a broader cultural and economic development strategy, the Municipality invests in cultural infrastructure and events that support this sector. This includes funding for local artists, cultural festivals, and creative projects that contribute to the cultural vibrancy of the region. The Municipality also actively promotes local artists and creative professionals through exhibitions, performances, and other public events, encouraging collaboration between the creative sector and other industries, such as technology, tourism, and education (Município de Torres Vedras, 2025). Scholars draw attention, however, that cultural practices can revitalise public spaces and enhance civic participation, but may also reinforce existing social hierarchies and exclusions (Fortuna, Ferreira, & Abreu, 1999).

To conclude, civic spaces in Torres Vedras are developed through a combination of municipal initiatives, community involvement, and cultural programming aimed at fostering social cohesion, civic engagement, and cultural enrichment. The local government, along with various organisations and community groups, plays a significant role in creating and maintaining these spaces.

3.2 The Legal Framework of Civic Spaces

The regulatory framework regulating civic spaces in Portugal is well-established and is primarily based on the **Portuguese Constitution** and various national laws. An in-depth analysis of this framework, including policies and institutions, was elaborated by OECD (2023), in its country report on civic spaces of Portugal.

Two articles of the Portuguese Constitution are particularly important in relation to civic spaces. Mainly, Article 26 recognises fundamental rights such as the right to personal identity, freedom of expression, private and family life, and protection against discrimination. It also guarantees the right

to legal protection against the misuse of personal information. Subsequently, article 109 Emphasises the importance of citizens' political participation, stating that the direct and active participation of men and women in political life is fundamental for consolidating the democratic system. The law must promote equality in the exercise of civic and political rights and non-discrimination.

Several other national legislations ensure the protection of civic spaces, mainly in relation to the freedom of expression and information (Law no.2/1999 addressing media freedom; public access to information and transparency Law no.26/2016 ensuring public access to information and Law no. 58/2019 regulating and protecting personal data) and non-discrimination (The Penal Code and the Civil Code). These are further executed through national transversal strategies adopted by the government.

The evolution of Torres Vedras' policies towards civic spaces reflects a gradual shift from addressing basic infrastructure needs to a more complex approach focused on increasing public participation, social inclusion, and sustainable urban development. Following the end of the dictatorship in 1974, the Municipality was elevated to city status in 1979, marking a period focused on electrification, piped water distribution, and road construction to improve the quality of life for residents. During the 1980s and 1990s, the focus shifted to urban development and land use planning, with little emphasis on civic spaces or public participation. However, in the 2000s, Torres Vedras began to prioritise the revitalisation of public spaces and the promotion of participatory democracy, particularly through mechanisms like Participatory Budgeting, which allowed citizens to influence the allocation of municipal funds. In recent years, the Municipality has developed a wide range of policies and programmes aimed at fostering civic spaces and community engagement.

The Municipality has the autonomy to create participatory processes, either addressing the entire population or tailored to specific demographic groups, with special attention given to youth and the elderly through initiatives such as the Youth Plan, participatory budgeting for youth ideas, We are citizen reporters programme, support for Senior Clubs, and lifelong learning opportunities, alongside a Strategic Plan for Aging. Some examples of civic spaces developed with the Municipality's support are presented further on in this Chapter.

Today, the Municipality of Torres Vedras places a strong emphasis on making civic spaces accessible and inclusive for all residents, including people with disabilities, and continues to prioritize community engagement across different demographic groups, such as youth, seniors, and migrants. The legal framework is perceived as a supportive one, although bureaucratic hurdles can slow down the development of civic spaces.

3.3 The Common Understanding of Civic Spaces

Because Portuguese legislation and society lack a common definition of 'civic spaces,' it is interesting to identify the most common concepts linked to its interpretation. This is done by key-word-frequency counting in the additions to the B.RIGHT SPACES working definition of 'civic spaces', on which 30 Portuguese survey respondents provided feedback. Most of them represent civil society organisations, followed by public administration and social economy associations.

All respondents agreed with the definition provided by B.RIGHT SPACES but offered suggestions for clarification. The most common terms included in these suggestions, aside from 'civic space', suggest that civic spaces in Portugal are characterized by a commitment to inclusivity, community-driven participation, and the integration of technology to support social cohesion and civic engagement in both urban and rural settings.

The term 'participation' signifies that civic spaces are or should be designed to encourage active engagement from citizens. This could involve community decision-making, local governance, or collaborative projects that empower individuals to contribute to their communities. Furthermore, the presence of 'technology' suggests that digital tools and platforms are likely being utilised or desired to enhance civic spaces. The prominence of terms like 'community', 'marginalised', 'diversity', 'include', and 'inclusion' underscores a focus on fostering inclusive civic spaces where diverse groups can engage. This implies that, based on the experience of the respondents, creating environments that are accessible and welcoming to all, regardless of background or identity, is an essential aspect of civic spaces.

The recurrence of the terms 'village' and 'social' indicates a strong link between civic spaces and social cohesion, particularly in smaller, rural communities. It suggests that civic spaces may play a role in preserving traditional village life while fostering social bonds and collective identity. Additional terms such as 'education', 'culture', and 'progress' appear to align with the suggestion from one expert interview [Expert Interview 9] that civic spaces are not only physical but also encompass ideas, beliefs, and spiritual elements.

Figure 8 Word cloud reflecting civic space understanding in Torres Vedras (PT)

Figure 9 Word cloud reflecting civic space understanding in Torres Vedras (EN)

3.4 *Civic Spaces in Practice*

This section provides further insights into civic spaces in Portugal based on two expert interviews conducted by the Municipality of Torres Vedras and EMERGE, as well as a series of examples of civic spaces from Torres Vedras.

Connecting people and civil society organisations working in different sectors with social economy organisations and public authorities should be an ongoing process. In Portugal, aligned with the previously outlined legal framework, the main actors involved in civic spaces are generally the state, local municipalities, and community organisations. However, there is a lack of coordination and communication among these entities, leading to poorly managed public spaces. The community is often weak, and there is a limited sense of shared responsibility [Expert Interview 9]. A successful example presented by [expert 8] is the [Oeiras Community Valley](#) programme, which effectively ensures the collaboration of different stakeholders, though to a lesser extent with the citizens.

Institutionalised forms of participation often suffer from limited citizen participation. Citizens may feel that their input is not genuinely considered, leading to a sense of tokenism or symbolic participation. A typical case occurs when public administrations create spaces for citizen input; however, the feedback is often not incorporated into decision-making, leading to frustration and disengagement. Another example involves social economy organisations that engage citizens in their activities, primarily in the management or strategic decision-making of the organisations themselves [Expert Interview 8]. Furthermore, income-generating activities in a civic space appear to be a ‘no man’s land’. An Expert Interview [9] suggests that such activities should be temporary and clearly defined to prevent compromising the civic nature of the space.

Self-organised civic spaces emerge from grassroots initiatives led by citizens or specific groups, often independent of institutional support. For example, in the Portuguese context, could be disability rights activism groups, which can be individually led, self-organised, and engaged in a variety of activities beyond advocacy, such as training and income generation. Additionally, when institutional support is lacking, civic spaces can serve as platforms for protests and resistance. However, these may often fail to change the status quo meaningfully [Expert Interview 9].

In Portugal, artistic activists who use art as a form of activism to raise awareness and advocate for social change are important actors in these spaces. Moreover, artistic contribution is valuable for transforming a public place into something more ‘meaningful’ and creating an atmospheric quality that encourages participation (or, in contrast, apathy) [Expert Interview 9]. Public art can play a role in creating an environment that fosters civic engagement. Therefore, in addition to legal and political frameworks, public art and education are key success factors for civic spaces, as both can cultivate a sense of community and shared responsibility.

Finally, the issue of protecting civic spaces is seldom addressed in public discourse in Portugal. Both social media and traditional media often oversimplify complex issues, resulting in minimal real debate or engagement with civic life [Expert Interview 8, 9]. In spite of these challenges, the Municipality of Torres Vedras, in cooperation with the local community, succeeds in developing key elements and venues for the local civic spaces. Some of the most prominent examples of programmes, initiatives and activities in this regard are outlined below.

Example 1: Public spaces rehabilitation

Urban Rehabilitation Areas (ARU) are designated zones that include buildings, infrastructure, facilities, and common spaces that are in deteriorating condition. Their designation aims to foster the rehabilitation of this part of the territory through integrated and thoughtfully planned interventions. To promote building rehabilitation and attract and retain residents, the Municipality offers support measures for interventions conducted within the defined ARUs. The management model for this initiative is founded on four principles, with the first being the principle of consultation. This involves establishing a dynamic and close relationship with the beneficiaries of the measures (residents, owners, traders, workers, users, etc.) and with various entities engaged in managing sectoral areas (culture, heritage, infrastructure, tourism, security, etc.) to reach a consensus, evaluate, and adapt the measures.

The Encosta Programme – The programme addresses the Urban and Social Regeneration of Encosta de São Vicente, located in the north of Torres Vedras. It emphasises the recovery and transformation of vacant, dilapidated, or ruined buildings and promotes the requalification of public spaces, including the creation of green areas. The Programme combines a series of structuring interventions centred around the former Municipal Slaughterhouse, with efforts focusing on public space, facilities, housing, and mobility.

Figure 10 The Encosta de São Vicente territory and the policies activated in the regeneration & development programme

Example 2: Social inclusion through art and cultural activities

[Centro De Artes e Criatividade - CAC](#) is a service that celebrates Carnival's artistic expressions and promotes social inclusion, creativity, and entrepreneurship. It aims to preserve and document the Torres Vedras Carnival collection and establish partnerships with universities and museums for national and international dissemination. Additionally, it promotes the development of artistic practices and creativity as a means of social inclusion, contributing positively to the sense of belonging among the communities of Encosta de São Vicente and the city of Torres Vedras.

[Somos Comunidade](#) is a project of Academico of Torres Vedras, designed for community intervention and social innovation in Encosta S. Vicente. The project aims to create a community newspaper and organise sociocultural activities on a weekly basis. Its main goal is to promote civic participation and social inclusion through the arts. The project specifically targets non-active seniors who may feel lonely or isolated. By using art as a tool, Somos Comunidade strives to address this issue and encourage seniors to engage more actively in their community.

It is noteworthy that Academico of Torres Vedras has engaged the local community in this neighbourhood by hosting a variety of events in the public spaces surrounding the community.

Figure 11 A contemporary art installation at CAC (artist: Matilde Cassani: "Esperou o Ano Inteiro")

Example 3: Social inclusivity

[Porta do Bairro](#) is an initiative designed to inspire self-care among the elderly across various domains, including physical, intellectual, emotional, social, and spiritual. The project is intended to benefit elderly residents living in the Encosta de São Vicente neighbourhoods of Torres Vedras, specifically Choupal, Forte, Cruz das Almas, Floresta, Matadouro, Reis, Barreto, and Amiais. To address the different domains of self-care, a wide range of activities has been organised. For the physical domain, physical education classes tailored to the condition of each senior are offered. For the intellectual, social, emotional, and spiritual domains, cookery workshops, sewing workshops, hairdressing workshops, preventive physiotherapy consultations, podiatry, and nutrition consultations are conducted. Additionally, a Psychosocial Intervention Office has been established with the aim of enhancing the living conditions of these individuals, as well as preventing and reducing phenomena of poverty and social exclusion.

[The Social Network \(Rede Social\)](#) is a local social network initiative aimed at promoting social development and combating poverty and social exclusion within the Municipality. It is part of a broader national programme in Portugal, which was established to foster collaboration among various stakeholders, including local government, non-governmental organisations, social institutions, and community members. The goal is to create a coordinated and integrated approach to address social issues and improve the quality of life for vulnerable populations. In Torres Vedras, Rede Social functions as a platform for dialogue, planning, and action, bringing together different actors to identify social needs, develop strategies, and implement projects that address those needs.

It operates through a Local Council and an Executive Secretariat, which coordinate efforts and ensure that resources are used effectively. The initiative also encourages participatory approaches, involving local residents in decision-making processes to ensure that interventions are tailored to the specific needs of the community.

3.5 Points for Further Reflection

This section presents some complementary ideas on the challenges, success factors, and recommendations for future actions to promote and protect civic spaces in Torres Vedras, as discussed in the Regional Board organised by the EMERGE association and the Municipality of Torres Vedras in November 2024.

Based on the previous sections, one can conclude that the foundation for civic spaces is well established within the Portuguese legal framework and, similarly, at the municipal level in Torres Vedras. At the local level, civic spaces are created through a combination of institutionalised Municipality-supported projects and self-organised initiatives, which strongly emphasise the inclusion of vulnerable groups and the promotion of community-level participation. However, the regional board highlights some challenges to the sustainability of these initiatives.

One of the primary issues is the **fragmented collaboration** between local authorities and community organisations. This gap often results in fragmented efforts, where resources and knowledge are not shared efficiently, leading to less impactful outcomes. Moreover, there are intrinsic power imbalances, tokenism, and limited citizen engagement in institutional spaces that, in theory, provide them with space for participation.

Second, **information barriers** pose a problem, as community members frequently struggle to access information about planning processes, funding opportunities, and available resources. This lack of transparency or comprehension can lead to disengagement and mistrust among residents, further complicating efforts to develop inclusive civic spaces.

Finally, **economic struggles and funding limitations** for civil society hinder the ability to launch or sustain community projects. Financial constraints often restrict the scope and longevity of initiatives, making it difficult to create and maintain effective civic spaces.

To address these challenges, several suggestions for improvement were proposed.

Two measures were recommended to overcome collaboration deficiencies. First, **partnership development** emerged as a key strategy, with a recommendation to form coalitions among local governments, non-profits, and community groups. By sharing resources, knowledge, and best practices, these partnerships could bridge gaps in collaboration and create more cohesive efforts. Second, **community engagement** was also highlighted as a crucial component, with a recommendation to organise regular workshops and forums to gather input and feedback from residents. This approach would ensure that their needs and preferences are central to planning efforts. Additionally, digital engagement strategies, such as social media, online surveys, and virtual town halls, could be utilised to reach a broader audience, particularly younger residents who may be less inclined to participate in traditional community meetings.

To tackle information barriers, **transparency initiatives** were proposed, with the suggestion to implement open data policies and public forums. These measures would ensure that community members are well-informed about decision-making processes, helping to reduce information barriers and foster greater trust and participation.

Finally, the importance of **monitoring and evaluation** was underscored regarding the economic viability of civic spaces. Developing specific metrics and indicators to measure the success of community projects—such as increased usage of public spaces or improved community satisfaction—would help track progress and ensure accountability. Structured channels for ongoing community feedback would also allow residents to voice their opinions and suggest improvements, creating a more dynamic and responsive approach to civic space development. Additionally, exploring funding opportunities was recommended, focusing on actively seeking out grants, sponsorships, and partnerships to secure financial resources. Collaborative grant applications could increase funding success rates and provide more sustainable financial support for community projects. Lastly, capacity building, including training sessions and workshops for community leaders, would enhance their skills in project management, advocacy, and community organising. As a result, they could be better equipped to lead initiatives effectively and potentially secure more funding while ensuring sustainability.

4. Civic Spaces in Warsaw

4.1 General Overview

In Poland, civil society has long been seen as a political project, playing a significant role in the country's independence and democratisation process. In Warsaw, in particular, civil society has complemented political society, with both fostering citizen engagement after 1989. Moreover, civil society enabled those hesitant to engage in formal politics to partake in civic activism that would benefit their neighbourhoods, thus contributing to the consolidation of democracy (Regulska, 2000). Active citizenship might also have been nurtured by how communities used public spaces

The conditions for civil society have greatly deteriorated since 2015, when the party Law and Justice took over the government. However, Polish civil society is more resilient than that of other countries in the region, being self-sustaining and diverse (Negri & Pazderski, 2021). Its work encompasses a variety of areas, advocating for causes ranging from environmental protection to reproductive rights, with citizen participation primarily driven by everyday social issues rather than political ideals (Stasiak & Wojtowicz-Jankowska, 2017). Increased civic activism and diversification of topics has been noted as the country's politics shifted to the right, including a broader scope beyond nationalist activism, such as urban activism, political protests, gender equality, education, climate and many others (Piotrowski, 2020).

Despite civil society comprising a diverse array of organisations, rich in experience and expertise, this has historically been ignored by decision-makers (Wygnański, 2020). There is a noticeable shrinkage of civic space for liberal, progressive organisations. However, forms of civic activism are also evolving, such as engaging in online activities, seeking societal support, strengthening their mission, collaborating, and creating civic networks (McMahon & Niparko, 2022) (Pospieszna & Pietrzyk-Reeves, 2022). Moreover, there is also a relatively high rate of informal political engagement.

The reconfiguration of civic space is driven by the government, owing to changes in regulations regarding access to state and foreign funding for civil society. Financial sustainability is one of the major struggles facing Polish CSOs, as much of their activity is project-based. Public funding remains the primary source of finance for many (Slavkova, Petrova, Sichtermann, & Moshelova, 2022). The challenge is that, nowadays, public funding is allocated in an arbitrary and non-transparent manner, with government-friendly organisations favoured not only in terms of funding but also through their involvement in public consultations and positions of power (Domaradzka & Kołodziejczyk, 2023). Additionally, limitations on the use of public space were established by the Act of Assemblies adopted in 2016. Consequently, a civic space that supports governmental objectives is being promoted, with a conservative civil society that absorbs democratic voices and space (Roggeband & Krizsán, 2021).

In this context, Warsaw, the 'rebel' Polish capital, remains at the forefront of safeguarding democratic values (Lasserre, 2019). The city's civic spaces have undergone significant transformations, reflecting its tumultuous history and changing ideologies (Skurowski, 2020). Despite facing challenges, Warsaw exhibits resilience and a strong capacity for civic engagement through urban movements that have cooperated with public administration in recent years (Oross & Kampka, 2024). Progressive civil society actively defends democratic values through protests (Lasserre, 2019), while citizens participate in the initiatives of the local government, NGOs, and informal groups to shape decision-making processes (Regulska, 2000).

The study of civic spaces in Warsaw is linked to the study of public spaces and their historical importance (Madanipour, Knierbein, & Degros, 2014) (Elzanowski, 2013), their actual use by different actors in the context of urban planning and environment (Filip, 2020), and migrants integration (Orchowska, 2024) (Horolets, Stodolska, & Peters, 2021) (Czepczyński, 2017). Interestingly, the development of civic spaces has also been attributed to the creative sector, which gradually contributed to increasing the city's attractiveness (Dudek-Mańkowska, Fuhrmann, Grochowski, & Zegar, 2012).

Nevertheless, discrepancies exist between formal structures and actual citizen involvement. An example of formal participation is the contribution to participatory budgeting as a practice of citizen involvement aimed at improving public spaces in major Polish cities. The level of participation in this practice varies significantly, with most engagement focusing on issues that address the immediate needs of the neighbourhoods and their residents. In Warsaw, the rate of civic engagement in participatory budgeting is among the highest compared to other major Polish cities (Szczepańska, Zagroba, & Pietrzyk, 2022).

When it comes to digital participation, in addition to facilitating participation in online consultations and petitions, the online environment fostered a more dynamic, informal, and ad-hoc form of activism centred on everyday issues rather than political ideals (Pietrzyk-Reeves, 2023). In the struggles between government and civil society, the internet became not only a tool of information but also for mobilisation, coordination, promotion of civic causes and crowdfunding (Domaradzka & Kołodziejczyk, 2023). In Warsaw, digital participation also serves as a potential mechanism for the co-creation of sustainable urban spaces (Szarek-Iwaniuk & Senetra, 2020).

Overall, the status of Warsaw's civic spaces continues to evolve, balancing historical memory, democratic aspirations, and economic pressures (Skurowski, 2020).

4.2 The Legal Framework of Civic Spaces and Key Stakeholders

The foundation for the development of civic spaces in Poland is laid by the **Constitution**, which safeguards the fundamental rights of freedom of expression and association (Article 54 on Freedom of Speech); freedom of assembly and association (Article 57 on the Right to Assembly); and access to services of general economic interest (Article 63 on the Right to Petition).

Furthermore, the **Act on Public Benefit Activity and Volunteer Work** (2003) establishes the criteria based on which organisations can operate as non-governmental organisations, the criteria that enable them to obtain public funding, as well as the rules for volunteering activities.

Local governments are responsible for implementing public policies at the local level that create opportunities for participation, including meetings, consultations, and information-oriented activities. These laws can define the civic spaces available for use and the extent to which local authorities can regulate these areas. National policies may impose certain standards or restrictions that local authorities must adhere to, affecting their ability to make decisions about civic spaces.

Warsaw, as a capital city, has a degree of autonomy established by Polish law, enabling it to tackle local issues, including the management of civic spaces. Nevertheless, this autonomy can be restricted by national policies that prioritize specific uses of land or public spaces, reflecting the interests of broader regional or national agendas.

Local actions regarding civic spaces can be influenced by national public policies. For instance, national initiatives focused on sustainability or urban development can shape local strategies for managing civic areas, encouraging local authorities to adopt specific practices or prioritize certain types of development.

Local authorities must also consider the voices of citizens and civic organisations that may advocate for particular uses of public spaces. While local government is closest to the community and often engages in public consultations, overarching policies or directives from national or regional governments may still affect how well they can respond to civic needs and activism.

In Warsaw, one of the City Hall departments is specifically tasked with [Strengthening the Local Community](#). This department is part of the [Municipal Communication Centre](#), and aside from communication and information-related tasks, it is responsible for a series of community-focused activities. These include strategic planning and programming for community strengthening within the broader urban revitalisation programme; it supports and coordinates local activity mechanisms, develops local activity spaces, promotes neighbourhood community activities and social inclusion, and fosters diversity and intergenerational dialogue. Additionally, the Municipality can allocate budgets for public areas, develop regulations for land use, and facilitate public consultations involving citizens in the decision-making process. The Municipality also implements participatory budgeting (*budżet partycypacyjny*), which allows residents to take part in the allocation of a portion of the city's budget.

Finally, the activities of NGOs are governed by the Act on Public Benefit Activity, the Act on Foundations and the Civil Code, which establish the criteria for registration, transparency, and accountability. Some NGOs benefit from tax exemptions, which promote charitable and social initiatives.

To conclude, Warsaw's **civic spaces are supported** by several key aspects that facilitate the functioning and growth of civil society in general and NGOs in particular. Firstly, NGOs benefit from **legal recognition** through national legal frameworks. These provide a solid foundation for the NGOs to form, operate, and access funding, ensuring their legitimacy and operational capacity. Secondly, **access to funding** is available through various state programmes, which support civil society initiatives and enable NGOs to carry out their missions. Thirdly, Warsaw hosts **an active civil society** that collaborates and networks effectively. This environment strengthens advocacy efforts and promotes resource sharing among organisations. Lastly, **public participation** is encouraged through legal frameworks that promote transparency and citizen involvement in decision-making, empowering NGOs to influence policies and advocate for their causes

However, there are notable **obstacles** that hinder the effectiveness of civic spaces. One major challenge is **regulatory complexity**, as NGOs face significant bureaucratic hurdles related to registration, compliance, and reporting requirements. These demands can be time-consuming and strain limited resources. Additionally, the **political climate** in Poland is often unstable, creating uncertainty for NGOs and affecting their long-term planning and operations. Finally, while funding opportunities exist, **funding instabilities** pose a risk, particularly for NGOs reliant on government support. Shifts in political priorities can lead to the withdrawal of funding for certain organisations or programmes, leaving them vulnerable and undermining their sustainability. These obstacles highlight the need for a more stable and supportive environment to ensure the continued growth and impact of civic spaces in Warsaw.

4.3 The Common Understanding of Civic Spaces

A formal definition of civic spaces is absent in Polish legislation. The 57 responses collected by FISE to the B.RIGHT SPACES scouting survey offer a glimpse of the common understanding of the term among Polish respondents. Particularly, their feedback on the project's definition provides suggestions on the perceived key elements of these spaces.

The proposed definition appeared the most unclear to the Polish survey respondents compared to those from other territories. Therefore, 'language' is among the most frequently used terms in the collected feedback. While this could be a translation nuance that highlights a fine line between the terms 'civic' and 'civil' (both potentially translated in Polish as 'obywatelski'), the confusion may also stem from the varied experiences of the respondents. Words such as 'political' and 'legal' contrasted with 'person', 'community' and 'action', which are all among the most used by the respondents, may suggest a tension between the top-down approach to civic spaces (political, legal) and bottom-up driven (by individual actions and community).

Interestingly, the term "political" was most frequently used by the Polish respondents compared to those from other surveys. This may suggest the impact of political decisions and strategies in shaping civic spaces. For instance, the establishment of MALs in Warsaw is linked to the city's political vision of being an "open city". It may also highlight the risks of civic spaces being exploited for political gain or subjected to changes in political leadership, which can affect their stability and effectiveness. Given the historical context, the term 'political' may also carry negative connotations, implying a connection with certain political entities or a lack of transparency. Conversely, its association with civic spaces might suggest that civic spaces serve as platforms for political resistance or advocacy, where communities unite to challenge or influence decisions on political issues. At the same time, the term "development" emphasises the ongoing evolution and expansion of civic spaces in Poland, particularly in urban areas like Warsaw. It indicates a focus on creating new spaces and enhancing existing ones to better serve communities. It may also reflect the significance of long-term strategies and policies aimed at fostering civic engagement and community development, such as the city's strategy for Local Activity Places. 'Development' could also suggest the necessity for sustainable models to ensure that civic spaces remain active and relevant over time, addressing challenges like funding and burnout.

Although these are primarily deductive ideas based on keyword analysis, they align with findings from expert interviews and the regional board, as further discussed.

Figure 12 Word cloud reflecting civic space understanding in Warsaw (PL)

Figure 13 Word cloud reflecting civic space understanding in Warsaw (EN)

4.4 Civic Spaces in Practice

This section gathers insights on how civic spaces are implemented in Warsaw, based on the context analysis elaborated by FISE and two expert interviews conducted by the organisation.

Civic spaces in Warsaw play an important role in the city's policy, with their development integrated into the current urban strategy. They often receive support from municipal cultural institutions and district cultural centres. The expansion of these spaces is shaped by city policies focused on fostering local communities and peripheral areas. In recent years, the city's cultural policy has shifted towards more human-centred issues, which accelerated the growth of civic spaces [Expert Interview 11].

The city's strategy includes the creation of **Local Activity Places** (Miejsca Aktywności Lokalnej or MAL), a Warsaw-specific example of civic spaces. MALs are a significant trend in Warsaw, often established within cultural centres or libraries (the model of integrating MALs into cultural centres and libraries is described as a "replicated model" in Warsaw). These spaces are designed to be accessible and inclusive, focusing on local community engagement and providing resources for community activities. MALs aim to promote integration and community building, fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility. Among the activities they offer are neighbourly breakfasts, family workshops, and cultural events. These activities are typically free of charge, adhering to the principle of non-financial barriers to entry, although there may be costs associated with hiring experts for specific events. While MALs are networked, there is limited institutional support for joint initiatives or collaborations between different civic spaces. Relationships between spaces are primarily based on personal connections and informal exchanges among coordinators. The Centre for Social Communication organises training and meetings for MAL staff, but formal collaboration between spaces is rare.

Examples of Local Activity Places:

- **MAL Białołęka:** An innovative civic space that started as "three rooms with a kitchen". This space was one of the early examples of civic spaces in Warsaw, focusing on grassroots, community-driven activities.

- **MAL “[The Well](#)”**: The Place of Local Activity “The Well” is a space for Bielany residents designed to support creative activities, strengthen neighbourhood ties, and inspire joint proactive participation.
- **MAL [Grójecka 109](#)**: A MAL located in a **revitalised former retail pavilion**. The space was part of a larger urban development project where neighbouring pavilions were demolished, and the remaining one was repurposed for community use. It provides space and equipment, and animators working there support residents in organizing events and help promote their activities. The main goal is to activate and integrate residents and build a local community based on openness, trust and reciprocity.

The institutionally supported civic spaces, such as MALs, have the advantage of a sense of stability, continuity, and visibility for initiatives. However, this comes with the necessity of functioning within specific institutional frameworks (for example, defined visual identification, communication strategies, etc.). Being part of an institution also means civic spaces are dependent on decisions made by the supervisory body.

Self-organised civic spaces, such as the grassroots movements in the Praga District of Warsaw, focused on zero-waste initiatives, including clothing and food processing, have the advantage of operating independently of the institutional support framework [Expert Interview 11]. They are also particularly important for giving a voice to disadvantaged groups, and resource allocation for these movements is vital, as they amplify unheard voices [Expert Interview 12].

In terms of sustainability, the grassroots movement may resist cooperating with institutions that can facilitate access to physical and financial resources. Grassroots initiatives often encounter challenges related to burnout and sustainability, as they depend largely on the passion and energy of particular individuals. Institutional support can help alleviate these challenges by offering financial and organisational stability, but there is a risk that such structures may not be as responsive to actual community needs [Expert Interview 12].

An example of a grassroots civic space is [Kraina Foundation](#). This emerged from a strong community need, providing assistance for residents at the escalation of the war in Ukraine and acting as a self-help centre collecting and distributing donations for Ukraine. Based on these community-supported activities, the Foundation was established. Currently, it engages in various social, intercultural, and environmental activities and has managed to sustain itself through community support and donations.

Civic spaces organised purely as resistance are perceived as short-lived [Expert Interview 11], but they can also formalise and become viable. An example is [Gniazdo](#), which emerged from the youth climate strike and still serves as a place of resistance and civic engagement.

Formally established NGOs may receive funding from several sources: public funding from the government and the Municipality in the form of grants or subsidies that support activities addressing social needs, EU funding, private donations and sponsorships, and, increasingly, crowdfunding. However, economic fluctuations can lead to reduced funding from both public and private sources, placing financial strain on NGOs. In Warsaw, there is a strong emphasis on keeping civic spaces free from commercial activities. At the same time, this raises dilemmas about sustainability, as maintaining these spaces incurs costs that need to be covered. Some spaces have had to give up their open space formula due to financial constraints, highlighting the need for sustainable funding models [Expert Interview 12].

Civic spaces in Warsaw are at times located in highly accessible and visible areas, such as near metro stations, making them easily reachable for the public. The design of these spaces emphasises

openness and inclusion, with many events open to all without the need for prior sign-ups. Nevertheless, subjects related to civic spaces are not heavily covered by traditional media, which tends to focus on global issues rather than local initiatives. However, social media plays a significant role in spreading awareness about these spaces. On social media, public discourse around civic spaces is growing, with more people becoming aware of the opportunities for community engagement and participation [Expert Interview 11].

Overall, civic spaces in Warsaw are characterized by a dynamic interplay between institutional support and grassroots initiatives. While grassroots groups bring authenticity and responsiveness to community needs, institutions provide stability and resources. The success of these spaces depends on effective collaboration, sustainable funding, and the dedication of individuals managing them. A significant challenge is the lack of joint initiatives connecting different civic spaces. Moreover, the relationships between these spaces are primarily based on human resources, exchanges among their coordinators, and the connections they cultivate. Currently, there are no institutional forms of support for exchanges, such as joint events. Civic spaces primarily focus on their own missions and goals while working with their local communities. The challenge lies in balancing the need for inclusivity and accessibility with the practicalities of sustainability and resource management. Most importantly, as an interviewed expert [11] stressed, kindness and inclusivity should remain the fundamental guiding principles of civic spaces despite the challenges they face.

4.5 Points for Further Reflection

The challenges faced by civic spaces and their supporting factors were further discussed by the Polish Regional Board, organised by FISE, in November 2024. This section highlights the key additional points raised during the discussion as food for thought regarding measures to strengthen civic spaces in Warsaw.

Four categories of challenges were identified: sociological, political, resource-related, and awareness-related. Although some were mentioned in the earlier analysis based on literature, the expert interviews, and the experience of FISE, others added more nuance to the discussion.

Sociological challenges include, from the perspective of the Regional Board, differences in demographic and social backgrounds, which lead to diverse values, languages, experiences, and expectations that, if unaddressed, could lead to tensions in civic spaces, discrimination, and misunderstandings. In addition to insufficient governmental support and political instability, the mutual lack of trust between the main stakeholders of civic spaces (administrations and civil society) can hinder the sustainability of these spaces and their freedom to choose activities. The lack of resources for civic spaces pertains not only to human and financial capacity but also to the physical infrastructure, which is sometimes inadequate or poorly equipped to develop into a civic space. Lastly, limited outreach regarding the impact of civic spaces, as well as unclear benefits of participation, restrict civic engagement.

Further discussion and collaboration between public authorities and other actors involved in civic spaces are necessary to align and comprehend what civic spaces actually exist in Warsaw. Currently, various forms of civic initiatives, such as community centres, welfare centres, foundations, and informal groups, can be categorised under this label. Furthermore, the lack of consolidation among these groups diminishes their advocacy efforts. Formal regulations may be required to ensure a systematic approach and effective functioning of civic spaces. This is particularly important as the civic spaces established by local authorities are often motivated by political incentives rather than real community needs.

5. Concluding Remarks

This report aims at reflecting the diversity of civic spaces at a micro level in the partner territories of the B.RIGHT SPACES project. Based on recent research, analysis of legal frameworks, and inputs from various stakeholders, we seek to deepen the understanding of different experiences of civic spaces locally, highlighting their multiple and unique nuances and peculiarities. This effort fosters knowledge exchange and the sharing of good practices among the project territories. Additionally, the document can serve as both an inspiration and a reflective resource for stakeholders interested in the factors that influence civic space development (whether enhancing or hindering it), as well as potential strategies for its protection and promotion

A series of **similar conditions** that enable the development of civic spaces are shared between the region of Catalonia, the metropolitan city of Rome, Turin, Warsaw and Torres Vedras. From the legal point of view, in all these territories, the foundation for the functioning of civic spaces is laid out in **the Constitution**, which guarantees fundamental rights such as freedom of assembly, expression, and participation. These rights form the basis for civic spaces in each region. Moreover, their constitutional frameworks are also fully aligned with the **EU Charter of Fundamental Rights**, reinforcing a shared commitment to protecting and promoting civic spaces.

All the investigated territories emphasise **decentralisation**, granting local authorities (such as municipalities) a key role in managing and regulating civic spaces. While local administrations have the autonomy to enable, promote, and protect these spaces through various local regulations, their actions remain subject to national policies.

Furthermore, in all these territories, there are **legal provisions and initiatives to promote citizen participation in civic spaces**, such as public consultations and participatory budgeting, which are common participatory methods across the territories, but also through tailored mechanisms of involvement specific to the local contexts. **Collaboration** between public institutions, private entities, and community organizations in managing civic spaces is overall encouraged, albeit with various degrees of acceptance. For example, in Catalonia, there is a strong preference for community-managed civic spaces, while in Warsaw, the default management of local spaces for activity falls under the responsibility of public authorities.

Simultaneously, **all regions face challenges** related to legal and regulatory hurdles, such as unclear definitions and complex bureaucracies, fragmented collaboration and coordination among different actors in civic spaces, resource constraints, the lack of sustainability of initiatives, and social and cultural challenges, particularly regarding inclusivity and limited citizen engagement, despite participatory policies.

There is no widely accepted **definition** of civic spaces in any region, and implicitly, there are no national standards for their operation and protection. The common understandings of civic spaces – be those community spaces, poli civici or spaces for local activity - reflect diverse key elements that may be included in each territory, ranging from a community empowerment focus in Catalonia to a focus on social needs, according to Italian respondents, inclusivity in Torres Vedras, and political developments in Warsaw. Naturally, these are complementary aspects, present to varying extents in all territories. What is specific is how they are reflected in the local implementation of civic spaces.

Although all territories share a focus on social and solidarity economy, this focus appears to be particularly strong in Catalonia. Catalonia, Rome, and Turin all emphasise their historical and cultural heritage, as reflected in laws pertaining to cultural heritage protection and citizen participation, along

with specific regulations for managing common goods and urban regeneration. Warsaw and Torres Vedras also emphasise urban revitalisation, though they express this focus through different approaches, ranging from local activity spaces integrated into the city to the revitalisation of cultural spaces and activities in the latter case. Overall, all territories feature civic spaces that strive for community strengthening.

To address these challenges, a series of measures can be proposed.

Firstly, at a regulatory level, having **a clear definition of civic spaces** could help harmonise regulations at different administrative levels. Moreover, legal frameworks should be enhanced to protect community-managed spaces from privatization and market-based solutions (Catalonia), as well as from politicization (Warsaw) and to preserve their overall autonomy (Rome, Turin). Bureaucratic processes can be streamlined to accelerate the development of civic spaces by simplifying procedures and reducing bureaucratic hurdles.

To **increase the financial sustainability of civic spaces**, the following suggestions arose during the projects' regional boards. First, enhancing public financial and infrastructural support should focus on community needs rather than political incentives. Second, securing funding for civic spaces could be achieved through public-private partnerships, and philanthropic support was encouraged. Third, civil society should explore funding opportunities through grants, sponsorships, and collaborative grant applications.

In line with this, developing **metrics** to measure the success of civic spaces can help track their impact on social cohesion and community engagement. By establishing **clear indicators**, such as increased usage of public spaces or improved community satisfaction, stakeholders can ensure that civic spaces are meeting their intended goals. These systems should focus on both quantitative and qualitative measures, such as the number of participants, the diversity of activities offered, and the level of community satisfaction. By regularly evaluating the performance of civic spaces, these regions can identify areas for improvement and ensure that resources are used effectively.

A **stronger collaboration** between public institutions, community organizations, and private entities through legal reforms and resource-sharing mechanisms is generally encouraged. Intermediary bodies, such as foundations, could facilitate dialogue. Formalized regulations to consolidate civic groups and improve coordination between public authorities and civil society could be beneficial. Such consolidation could also enhance knowledge and resource exchange.

Finally, there is a need to **raise public awareness** and understanding of the importance of civic spaces. This can be achieved through educational campaigns and community-driven initiatives that highlight the role of these spaces in fostering social cohesion and inclusion. Public authorities should work closely with civic organizations to promote the benefits of participation, utilising both traditional and digital platforms to reach a broader audience. Additionally, regular workshops and forums could be organized to gather input from residents, ensuring that their needs and preferences are central to planning efforts. Digital engagement strategies, such as social media and online surveys, can also be used to engage younger residents who may be less inclined to participate in traditional community meetings. By making civic spaces more visible in public discourse, along with their advantages, greater participation and ownership among citizens can be encouraged. Last but not least, targeted programmes should address the needs of marginalised groups and foster a sense of belonging among all community members.

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